

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNET MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SERVICES SECTOR

Kakhramonov Khurshidjon

PhD, Associate professor

Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract. This article addresses the issues of internet marketing in Uzbekistan and its application in the current context for promoting and selling services in the housing and communal services sector. The study provides a detailed examination of modern internet marketing tools, as well as methods for conducting various types of online marketing research. Existing internet marketing instruments are analyzed, alongside a review of digital platforms used for marketing activities. The effectiveness of these tools is assessed with regard to the current state of the utility services market in Uzbekistan and its specific characteristics.

Keywords: Internet marketing, information space, communication functions, digital tools, housing and communal services.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the rapid development of digital technologies and their penetration into various sectors of the economy, the housing and communal services (HCS) sector is also facing the need to adapt and implement modern approaches to management and communication. Internet marketing, as a vital tool in contemporary business strategies, offers unique opportunities for enhancing the efficiency of residential property management and improving engagement with service consumers.

The rapid digitalization of society and the widespread use of the Internet have significantly influenced consumer behavior. The Internet has become a primary

channel for accessing information, including the search for and selection of property management companies, highlighting the necessity of actively utilizing digital tools and platforms for attracting and retaining clients.

Amid growing public interest in transparency and accountability in the operations of management organizations, internet marketing provides effective instruments for open and constructive communication with customers. Social media platforms, customer reviews, and online ratings play a crucial role in shaping a company's reputation and fostering consumer trust.

The topic of internet marketing in the HCS sector is highly relevant, as it directly correlates with the digital transformation of society and the expanding role of the Internet in the economy and other areas of life. However, many enterprises within the housing and utilities sector have yet to fully recognize the importance of this tool or understand its potential impact on the efficiency of their commercial operations. This underlines the necessity of gaining a deeper understanding of internet marketing mechanisms and identifying the most suitable tools for application within this industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Internet marketing was first introduced in the 1990s, when websites—then entirely text-based—began to feature advertisements for goods and services [1]. In just a few decades, the Internet evolved from an auxiliary marketing tool into a primary channel of promotion; in some industries, it has nearly replaced traditional marketing practices.

As the Internet continues to develop, it simultaneously reshapes business practices and product promotion methods while significantly reducing operational costs. Today, entrepreneurs are required to engage in a new type of activity—internet marketing—which involves planning, analysis, control, organization, and strategy development aimed at maintaining customer relations via the Internet and

ultimately securing market presence.

The emergence and rapid growth of the Internet has led to ongoing challenges in forming a unified definition of internet marketing. Initially, at the dawn of commercial activity online—at the end of the 20th century—internet marketing was interpreted narrowly as the conduct of advertising campaigns through digital channels [2]. Some scholars defined it even more restrictively, equating it merely with banner advertising or avoiding a clear conceptualization of the term altogether.

According to V. Kholmogorov, internet marketing is defined as a set of methods that allow website owners to promote their digital resources and, consequently, enhance brand visibility and generate additional profits for their businesses [3].

Despite the above, it is evident that most attention has historically been given to internet advertising rather than to marketing research within the online space.

A significant advancement in the field came from the approach proposed by V.V. Dik, A.E. Rodionov, and M.G. Luzhetsky. They defined internet marketing as a set of measures aimed at exploring the online market environment and promoting goods and services through modern technologies. This perspective highlights the essential role of full-scale marketing research as a foundation for successful online promotion efforts [4].

Similarly, E.A. Petrik views marketing research as a core domain within internet marketing. Furthermore, he identifies the Internet itself as a novel space for economic activity—characterized by business models and processes that differ fundamentally from those of traditional commerce [5].

Internet marketing is broadly understood as a set of activities aimed at improving a website's ranking in search engines, increasing traffic, and consequently attracting new clients and fostering business growth. The terms search engine optimization (SEO) and website promotion are commonly used to describe specific strategies that enhance a site's visibility in search engine results.

While high daily visitor numbers are often seen as the primary goal of web marketing, its ultimate objective lies in attracting the greatest number of clients from a specific target market segment.

The evolution of marketing in the housing and communal services (HCS) sector differs substantially from the broader marketing field, which defines its unique characteristics [6]. During the Soviet era, the HCS market was monopolized by state-run enterprises assigned to serve a predetermined number of consumers. These consumers had no choice in service providers, rendering marketing campaigns and research irrelevant. Over the past decade, however, the Uzbek government has initiated reforms aimed at gradually transforming the HCS sector into an efficient market-oriented system [7].

As a result, licensed management companies have emerged as intermediaries between service providers and consumers, along with homeowners' associations. This shift introduced consumer choice into the HCS market, thereby creating the need for structured and strategic marketing efforts in this field.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The theoretical foundation of this research is based on methodological approaches to defining marketing within the housing and communal services (HCS) sector, as well as frameworks for effective marketing management in urban housing administration. These approaches are grounded in the scholarly works of both domestic and international researchers.

The study of the applied aspects of marketing management in the HCS sector was conducted using a combination of empirical and theoretical research methods, including observation, comparison, analysis, classification, as well as analytical and statistical grouping techniques.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Overall, marketing in the housing and communal services (HCS) sector can be defined as a process of developing and promoting services related to the improvement of residents' living conditions. This includes water supply, electricity provision, heating, maintenance of adjacent areas, upkeep of residential buildings, tariff policies, service performance analysis, and fostering a positive perception of the service provider among consumers.

Marketing management in the HCS sector encompasses several key areas, including the coordination of marketing activities by service providers and intermediary organizations (see Figure 1).

The specificity of marketing management in the housing and communal services (HCS) sector lies in the inapplicability of direct marketing techniques and the use of the marketing mix under quasi-market conditions.

While the marketing mix is present in the HCS sector, it is implemented through the adaptation of tools and methods to the specific nature of the industry and its interaction with the external environment [8]. Marketing research also plays a crucial role in the contemporary HCS market, serving as a foundation for commercial decision-making and enabling more effective satisfaction of consumer needs. This, in turn, contributes to maintaining and enhancing the enterprise's competitiveness.

Figure 1. Structure of Marketing Management in the Housing and Communal Services Sector (HCS)

In the context of the housing and communal services (HCS) sector, marketing research does not significantly differ from similar practices in other industries or areas of commercial activity. It involves the collection, processing, and analysis of information about consumers and competitors. As a result, marketing research enables management companies to obtain up-to-date data on the external environment, identify existing problems and available resources, and build a sequence of actions to develop appropriate problem-solving strategies.

Modern internet marketing tools make it possible to collect and analyze large volumes of consumer data, which enhances the precision of targeted advertising campaigns and improves personalized service delivery. This, in turn, can lead to higher levels of customer satisfaction and the optimization of internal business processes.

Marketing research in the housing and communal services sector can be classified into several types, depending on the objectives pursued:

- Resource analysis
- Monitoring of the socio-economic situation
- Consumer market research
- Competition monitoring
- Social monitoring (feedback from the population)
- Comprehensive marketing analysis of municipal business projects

Based on data collection methods, marketing research in the housing and communal services (HCS) sector can be classified as follows:

- Field research (based on the collection, processing, and analysis of primary data)
- Desk research (involving the study and evaluation of secondary data)
- Combined research

Marketing communications play an essential role in the housing and communal services (HCS) sector. These communications involve processes aimed

at delivering information to a target audience, which, in the case of a management company, includes both potential and current consumers. Through marketing communications, a company establishes interaction with stakeholder groups interested in cooperation. The effectiveness of a marketing campaign often depends on how well the communication system is structured and implemented.

In the HCS sector, both traditional offline and modern online contact points are used for marketing communications.

Offline contact points include: mass media, brochures, signage, flyers, bulletins, handouts, the company office, and employee uniforms.

Online contact points include: social media platforms, contextual advertising, messenger chats and channels, video hosting platforms, and others [9].

The primary distinction between internet marketing and traditional marketing lies in its execution within a virtual environment. Nevertheless, both small and medium-sized businesses, including enterprises in the HCS sector, face numerous challenges during the transition to digital platforms.

The internet possesses several unique characteristics that differentiate digital marketing from traditional approaches. For example, once information is posted online, it cannot be completely removed—this can be both an advantage and a drawback for service-oriented businesses [10]. Furthermore, online marketing campaigns are highly hypervisual, enhancing the effectiveness of viral marketing. The rapid speed at which promotional messages spread online also makes it more difficult to predict the outcomes of marketing efforts.

Despite the considerable potential of internet marketing in the HCS sector, there is a lack of systematic research focused on evaluating the effectiveness of different strategies in this area. This creates a need for scientific analysis that could provide practical recommendations for management companies seeking to optimize their marketing approaches.

Traditional marketing typically requires significant financial investment,

which is often unaffordable for most enterprises in the HCS sector. In contrast, many challenges can be resolved faster and at lower cost through internet-based tools compared to offline marketing.

It is worth noting that the concept of relationship marketing places greater emphasis on communication than does classical marketing theory. The foundation of tactical communication planning with target audiences includes:

- quantitative and qualitative composition of target segments (identifying needs, levels of expectations, purchasing power, etc.);
- structure and content of communication messages;
- selection of the most cost-effective communication channels and allocation of resources by the management organization.

Since all expenses, including those related to advertising, must be incorporated into the annual budget and approved by the residents, significant expenditures on communication activities are virtually excluded. Therefore, management organizations face the complex task of identifying effective low-cost platforms for interacting with consumers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is important to emphasize that the problem examined in this study is indeed highly relevant. Modern consumers expect companies to keep pace with technological progress. Over the past two decades, consumer behavior has undergone a fundamental transformation—expectations toward companies have increased, and attitudes toward advertising have significantly changed. At the same time, the Internet has provided modern businesses with a wide array of opportunities: new tools, the ability to scale quickly and easily, cost-effective promotion, and closer interaction with consumers.

The housing and communal services (HCS) sector is traditionally viewed as a conservative industry, resistant to technological innovation and characterized by

significant technological lag and chronic underfunding. The effectiveness of smart technology development in the HCS sector is entirely determined by consumer needs and preferences, their level of satisfaction, and their engagement in the sector's development. Moreover, the selection, financing, and implementation of smart technologies in the management of multi-apartment buildings is de jure impossible without approval by residents at general homeowners' meetings.

Therefore, the advancement of smart technologies in the HCS market can only be achieved through the integration of modern relationship marketing tools into the activities of management organizations. This requires the identification of actual resident needs and the development of targeted smart solutions that align with the expectations of specific consumer audiences.

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